

Enhanced carbon-based back contact electrodes for perovskite solar cells: effect of carbon paste composition on performance and stability

Mozhdeh Forouzandeh^{a,d,*}, Maryam Heidariramsheh^a, Hamid Reza Heydarnezhad^b, Hafez Nikbakht^c, Maurizio Stefanelli^c, Luigi Vesce^{c,*}, Nima Taghavinia^{a,*}

^a Nanoparticles and coatings lab, Department of Physics, Sharif University of Technology, Tehran 14588, Iran

^b Department of Polymer Engineering and Color Technology, Amirkabir University of Technology, Tehran 1591634311, Iran

^c CHOSE (Centre for Hybrid and Organic Solar Energy), Department of Electronic Engineering, University of Rome Tor Vergata, Via del Politecnico 1, 00133 Rome, Italy

^d Solaires Enterprises Inc, Victoria, BC V9B 4G2, Canada

***Corresponding Author:** Nima Taghavinia, Mozhdeh Forouzandeh, and Luigi Vesce

Email: taghavinia@sharif.edu

mozhdeh@solaires.net

vesce@ing.uniroma2.it

Abstract:

To address the issue of cost and instability in perovskite solar cells (PSCs), it is promising to substitute the regular hole collecting electrode i.e., spiro-OMeTAD/Au with inorganic hole transport layer (HTL)/carbon electrode. In this study, three carbon pastes were investigated with different binders: polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), styrene-butadiene-styrene (SBS) and ethyl cellulose (EC). Carbon layers were compared in terms of mechanical stability, conductivity and performance as back contact electrodes in PSCs with an inorganic HTM composed of CuInS₂ nanoparticles. To assess mechanical properties of the carbon pastes, adhesion tests by using tape, ultrasonication in the media of deionized water and acidic deionized water, and also flexibility test were performed. The carbon layer based on SBS carbon paste (SBS-CP) was intact after adhesion tests and over 1017 cycles of flexibility test. The one based on PMMA carbon paste (PMMA-CP) didn't tolerate all mechanical tests and disintegrated. The carbon layer based on EC carbon paste (EC-CP) partly damaged after adhesion tests and didn't pass the flexibility test. The best efficiency of 18.6% was obtained for a device based on SBS-CP and significant shelf-life stability over 172 days stored in relative humidity of 40% and dark.

1. Introduction:

Notable progress in power conversion efficiency of perovskite solar cells in the last decade has led to the state-of-the-art efficiency of 26.1% [National Renewable Energy Laboratory efficiency chart] which is comparable with the commercial silicon and copper indium gallium selenide

(CIGS) solar cells. Perovskite photoactive layers take benefits of outstanding optoelectronic properties including broad light absorption range, a sharp optical absorption edge, a high absorption coefficient[1], a small exciton binding energy (≤ 10 meV), ambipolar charge transport, a long charge-carrier lifetime (≈ 1 μ s), and diffusion length (> 1 μ m)[2], low trap-state density, defect tolerance properties. In addition, the performance of perovskite solar cells has further advanced by convenient and low-cost solution-based fabrication process, composition engineering, suppression of trap-assisted recombination by passivation interlayers, and developing hole and electron transport layers.

However, the instability of PSCs originating from extrinsic and intrinsic factors[3–5] restricts the PSCs to commercialize. Degradation and instability of the solar cell often occur in the hole collecting layers (hole-transporting layer and cathode electrode). The common electrodes applied in the conventional PSCs are expensive metals such as gold. Gold is deposited using costly vacuum-based techniques, while penetrating gold in HTL and the PSK layer also leads to the device degradation[6].

Carbon allotropes have been used in various forms such as an additive, an interface layer[7–10], or one of the main layers in the configuration of perovskite solar cells[11]. In the latter case, PSCs are divided into three main categories: (1) mesoscopic PSCs, (2) HTL-free Carbon PSCs, (3) regular n-i-p structured carbon PSCs which is also considered in this study[12–19]. Carbon with a work-function of 4.6-5.0 eV is a suitable replacement for metals to apply in PSCs featured for long-term stability. Furthermore, carbon materials by taking advantage of low cost, feasible synthesis and deposition, high mechanical stability, abundance, hydrophobicity, being inert to ion migration have paved the way for using carbon electrodes in large scale and flexible PSCs. Therefore, the use of carbon is an important step to eliminate the complexity of the gold

deposition and reducing high costs on the large scale[20]. Carbon electrodes are used in the typical structures of planar and meso-porous perovskite solar cells. Moreover, carbon materials in role of electrode can stop either penetrating moisture and oxygen or escaping volatile perovskite components[21].

In regular n-i-p carbon-based PSCs, carbon layer is deposited on the hole transporting layer. Different kinds of carbon paste and graphite flakes using lamination or doctor blading methods are considered as carbon electrodes. To utilize a carbon paste as a back contact electrode in perovskite solar cells it is very important to consider (1): an appropriate solvent being compatible with a deposited perovskite layer. non-polar solvents such as chlorobenzene and toluene are applicable. (2): an optimized mixture of conductive carbon flakes, carbon black, and other carbon-based materials is necessary to obtain the required conductivity as well as connecting flakes with each other and underneath. (3): The binder of the carbon paste components must be well dissolved in the solvent and considering the carbon paste constituents, it is expected to help the paste with proper flow and adhesion. In addition to a bonding basic role, the binder can be liable to cover the flexibility of the paste which is very essential for fabricating flexible perovskite solar cells. (4): The rheology and coating method must also be optimized to achieve a uniform electrode with proper adhesion. Managing the two mentioned ideas can highly prevent some drawbacks of carbon deposition such as forming cracks, fragility, formation of porosity, gap, and incomplete connection with the substrate which consequently affect the hole carriers transfer from HTL to the electrode.

Solvent constituent of carbon paste can be controversial because polar solvent might destroy the perovskite layer and on the other hand non-polar solvent is not compatible with common organic HTL. For this reason, inorganic HTLs are more reasonable candidate than organic HTLs. Despite

achieving highly efficient PSCs by organic ones (especially Spiro-MeOTAD), they suffer from the poor stability[22]. Additives like LiTFSI and TBP added to the HTL in order to increase hole mobility are destructive factors due to their hygroscopic nature[23]. Inorganic hole-transporting materials (HTMs) in PSCs are more resilient (physically and chemically) to be degraded than organic HTMs without additives such as polymers, small molecules and organic-metallic compounds[24–28]. Inorganic copper-based HTMs with benefits of high mobility and suitable energy level are desirable HTMs. However, they are applied in inverted PSCs because of the demand of high temperature of about 200 °C (for calcination and elimination of organic compounds) which is destructive for organic-inorganic PSCs. Different inorganic HTL including $\text{CuIn}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{S}_2$, $\text{Cu}_2\text{Zn}_x\text{Sn}_y\text{S}_4$ have been developed in our group[29–31] which are compatible with the perovskite layer. These HTLs have shown not only inexpensive and feasible synthesis but also high conductivity, hole mobility, and stability in PSCs.

In this study, to further highlight the importance of the constituents of carbon paste applied in perovskite solar cells, three different carbon pastes with different components specially binder and solvent were compared in terms of adhesion to the substrate, flexibility, mechanical stability, and applying in PSCs as back contact electrodes. The compositions of the pastes are different in conductive part, solvent, and binder. The abbreviation of the binders has been considered to nominate the pastes: polymethyl methacrylate-based carbon paste (PMMA-CP), styrene-butadiene-styrene based carbon paste (SBS-CP) and ethyl cellulose-based carbon paste (EC-CP) (Table S1). In line with the goal of stability and price reduction, an inorganic HTM composed of CuInS_2 NPs covered by hydrophobic OLAM ligands was also applied. The results demonstrated an optimized combination of suitable adhesion either carbon particles to each other or the carbon layer to the substrate (which can be either glass or a stack of a PSC up to HTL), conductivity,

and being chemically compatible with perovskite material are necessary for a carbon paste to develop stable PSCs. By comparing PMMA-CP, SBS-CP, and EC-CP, the second one was recognized as an optimized carbon paste delivering the best efficiency of 18.6% (on 65th day of IV measurement) in an ambient environment and measured stability after 172 days of aging. Furthermore, carbon layers based on SBS-CP was verified the acceptable flexibility over 1017 bending cycles with no change in the layer and relatively invariant resistivity. The combination of Toluene, SBS, and conductive particles is well matched with the structure of PSCs. PSCs based on SBS-CP (SBS-CPSCs) are promising for commercializing and elevating the durability of PSCs.

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1. Fabrication

Etched glass/fluorine-doped tin oxide [FTO] sheets were ultrasonically washed with solutions of detergent, deionized water, ethanol, acetone, isopropanol. After heating at 500°C, the glass/FTO sheets were treated in UV-Ozone for 15 min. A solution of titanium diisopropoxide bis acetylacetonate (Aldrich) with a volume ratio of 1:15 in anhydrous ethanol (Merck) was sprayed onto the substrate at 250 °C temperature by spray pyrolysis and dried air. After sintering at 500 °C for 30 min, cooling down, and 15 min of UV-Ozon treatment, diluted TiO₂ paste (IRASOL) with the weight ratio of 1:5.5 was spin-coated on the substrates with the rate of 4000 rpm for 20 s. The deposited substrates were heated at 100 °C for 10 min and transferred to the furnace to sinter at 500 °C for 30 min. The triple cation PSK solution of Cs_{0.05}(MA_{0.83}FA_{0.17})_{0.95}Pb(Br_{0.17}I_{0.83})₃ was selected to be deposited as the absorber layer.

To form the mixed-halide PSK as the absorber layer, the solution of $(\text{Cs}_{0.05}(\text{MA}_{0.83}\text{FA}_{0.17})_{0.95}\text{Pb}(\text{Br}_{0.17}\text{I}_{0.83})_3)$ was prepared using anhydrous solvent of DMF: DMSO (4:1), solutions of PbI_2 (in the solvent (1.5 M)), PbBr_2 (in the solvent (1.5 M)), $\text{FAI}(\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)_2\text{I})$ (in the PbI_2 solution (1.2 M)), MABr ($\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{Br}$) (in the PbBr_2 solution (1.2 M)), and CsI (1.5 M in DMSO). The related deposition process is a one-step procedure involved spinning the prepared solution at 1000 rpm for 10 s and subsequently injecting 250 μl of the anti-solvent of chlorobenzene onto the substrate during spinning at 4000 rpm for 20 s. The process was followed by annealing at 100°C for 1 h to accelerate the crystallization of PSK grains.

CHOSE part:

Fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO)-glass substrate (TEC7, Pilkington) were subjected to etching by using a picosecond UV laser to insulate the two electrodes of the cell (2.5x2.5 cm², 0.5 cm² active area). The etched samples were rinsed in a solution of deionized water and helmanex, followed by a wash with deionized water to remove any remaining soap residue. Acetone and 2-propanol were utilized for a 10-minute cleaning process in a sonicator. Prior to the deposition of SnO_2 , an extensive 20-minute UV-Ozone treatment was administered to eradicate organic residues from the surface. To prepare the SnO_2 nanoparticle ink, the commercial SnO_2 dispersion (Alfa Aesar colloidal dispersion 15% in water) was diluted with deionized water at a 1:5 volume ratio. The diluted SnO_2 dispersion was then deposited onto the substrate by using the blade coating technique. Consecutively, the α -FAPbI₃ perovskite in DMF/DMSO was deposited onto the substrate by blade coating technique. The blade coating deposition process is assisted by a controlled and heated airflow to pre-dry the perovskite surface. A subsequent anti-solvent step (IPA from Sigma Aldrich) is performed with the same deposition method. Finally, the substrates are annealed at 150 °C on a hot plate for 20 min. Blading and drying systems are placed at a

precise distance from each other and can be controlled via software by the user. Once cooled down to room temperature, PEAI was applied to the perovskite layer through blade coating. Moving forward, the CIS nanoparticle solution was spin-coated onto the samples at 3000 rpm for 20 seconds under ambient conditions. The coated samples were subsequently annealed at 120°C for 20 minutes.

After cooling down, the substrates were spin coated by CuInS₂ ink (IRASOL) as an HTM at 3000 rpm for 30 s and heated at 100 °C for 10 min. This step was repeated the same for the second deposition. Then carbon paste was deposited onto the substrate by the doctor blade method. The residual solvent in the PMMA-CP, SBS-CP, and EC-CP was evaporated by heating the devices in an oven at 100 °C for 30 min. For the part that was done at CHOSE, as well as SBS-CP a carbon back contact (Dyename) was deposited onto the samples using blade coating technique, followed by annealing at 120 °C for 15 minutes.

The PMMA-CP was prepared by ball-milling carbon black and graphite flakes, with the weight ratio of 2:3 carbon black to graphite for 10 h to form a carbon mixture. The carbon paste was prepared by adding and mixing chlorobenzene as solvent and dissolved polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) in chlorobenzene as the binder. The prepared paste was deposited directly on the substrates using the doctor blade method. Prepared devices were heated in an oven set to 100 °C for 15 min just after depositing carbon paste.

The SBS-CP was prepared by ball-milling carbon black and graphite flakes, with the weight ratio of 1:1 carbon black to graphite for 10 h to form a carbon mixture. The carbon paste was prepared by adding and mixing toluene as solvent and dissolved styrene-butadiene-styrene (SBS) in toluene as the binder. The prepared paste was deposited directly on the substrates using the

doctor blade method. Prepared devices were heated in an oven set to 100 °C for 30 min just after depositing carbon paste.

The general composition of EC-CP includes graphite flakes (3.187 μm, purchased from HomyTech, Taiwan), carbon black (26-30 nm, purchased from HomyTech, Taiwan), P25 powder, ethyl cellulose (SigmaAldrich 46070), and terpineol (Merck 814759). Ethanol (Merck) was also used in the dispersion stage. In order to prepare carbon paste, first, 0.6 g of ethyl cellulose with a mixture of carbon black powders (0.24 g), graphite (0.72 g), P25 (0.24 g), and appropriate ethanol were weighed in an appropriate balloon. The ultrasonic homogenization was then performed using a Ti-horn-equipped sonicator (Hielscher). The ultrasonic homogenization was again performed for 5 minutes. Finally, terpinol was added to this mixture under stirring. The balloon was vacuum-dried to remove the ethanol completely.

2.2. Characterization:

Field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) images of samples were recorded by a TESCAN field emission SEM instrument. The synthesized nano particles were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) (X'Pert PRO MPDPANalytical Company), transmission electron microscopy (TEM) (Tecnai-Osiris) equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analyzer. The ultraviolet–visible (UV–vis) absorption/transmission spectra were recorded with a PerkinElmer Lambda 25 spectrophotometer equipment. The steady-state photoluminescence spectra were measured using Avantes TEC-2048 spectrometer under the illumination of diode laser with wavelength of 405 nm (the illumination was from the glass side). The current density-voltage curves were recorded under AM1.5 standard illumination using Palmsens potentiostat source meter at a scan rate of 5 mV s⁻¹ and in the reverse voltage sweeping direction without any precondition and IRASOL SIM1020 solar simulator. The area of

C-PSCs 0.096 cm^{-2} . The incident photons to current conversion efficiency (IPCE) were measured by IPCE-020 IRASOL instrument. Impedance spectroscopy was done using potentiostat galvanostat-PGE 18 (IRASOL) and a white LED light source in the frequency range of 200 kHz to 1 Hz under 0.1 SUN illumination and applying 0 V, 0.2 V, 0.4 V, 0.6 V, 0.8 V, and V_{oc} . The measured frequency-dependent resistances were normalized to the PSC's active area.

CHOES part:

The photovoltaic characteristics are measured with a class A sun simulator (Sun 2000, Abet) at AM 1.5 1000 W/m^2 calibrated with an SKS 1110 sensor (Skye Instruments Ltd., Llandrindod Wells, UK); the system is equipped with a 2612 source meter (Keithley Instruments Inc., Cleveland, OH, USA) and a LabVIEW interface. The IPCE equipment (Arkeo) is from Cicci Research.

3. Results and discussion:

The sheet resistance and resistivity of the carbon layers deposited by doctor-blade method were measured and presented in Table 1. The thicknesses of 120, 143, and $106 \mu\text{m}$ ($\pm 0.01 \mu\text{m}$) for PMMA, SBS, Ethyl Cellulose based carbon layer (to easy reference of the mentioned layers: PMMA-CP, SBS-CP, and EC-CP were chosen respectively) were obtained by a micrometer. The slight difference comes from the composition of each paste. The lowest resistivity belongs to PMMA-CP with the amount of $0.0473 \Omega \text{ cm}$ which is about half and third of the resistivity belonging to SBS-CP and EC-CP (0.0932 and $0.1426 \Omega \text{ cm}$, respectively). The difference among the resistivity of the deposited pastes may mainly originate from the conductive constituents and binder. The conductive part of the carbon paste involves the weight percent of carbon powder (graphite and carbon black) in the whole paste and also the ratio of the graphite to carbon black.

In addition, the resistivity of the binder used in the carbon paste impacts the conductivity of the paste. Considering the resistivity feature, the PMMA-CP seems to be superior to SBS-CP and EC-CP due to these properties which are 20% in weight percent of carbon, 40% in carbon black to carbon mixture ratio, and $10^{15} \Omega \text{ cm}$ in resistivity of PMMA. In contrast, EC-CP containing ethyl cellulose binder and P25 nanoparticles shows higher electrical resistance.

Tabel 1. Sheet resistance and resistivity of doctor-bladed carbon paste of PMMA-CP, SBS-CP, and EC-CP.

Carbon Paste	t (thickness) [μm]	V/I [Ω]	R_s [Ω/\square]= $4/53 \times (V/I)$	ρ ($R_s \times t$) [$\Omega \text{ cm}$]
PMMA-CP	120	0.87	3.94	0.0473
SBS-CP	143	1.44	6.52	0.0932
EC-CP	106	2.97	13.45	0.1426

According to the carbon electrode top scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) images (Fig. 1), the coverage of three carbon layers is comparable originating from their composition. The uniform and monolithic of the carbon layer based on SBS-CP (SBS-CL) can be observed in Fig. 1b. Holes on the surface of the one based on PMMA-CP (PMMA-CL) show less integrity compared to the one based on SBS-CP and big holes and cracks lie on carbon layer based on EC-CP (EC-CL) represent fragility which is unfavorable for flexible photovoltaics. Images of the scale of 500 nm for each carbon layer show a proper mixture of components. Worth noting that in the case of SBS-CP, thanks to the thermoplastic elastomer binder, a proper binding by the binder between the paste components is evident.

Fig. 1. a-c) Surface topography of different carbon layers based on PMMA-CP, SBS-CP, and EC-CP for two magnitudes of 500 nm and 1 mm.

To examine the adhesion of the deposited carbon layer components with each other and with the substrate, the adhesion test was performed by using the 3 M Scotch® Magic™ tape. In Fig. 2a, top and bottom layers represent the appearance of carbon layers before and after the adhesion test respectively. The SBS-CL and EC-CL look without changes, nevertheless, the PMMA-CL partly disintegrated and did not pass the test. This behavior indicates the unsuitability of PMMA binder to create proper adhesion in carbon layer. To further prove the adhesion of carbon layers at a harsh condition, the samples were subjected to an ultrasonication process in the media of deionized water. After one minute of sonication, the PMMA-CL was completely disintegrated presenting PMMA binder is not a suitable component in carbon paste for long term application like solar cells. The SBS-CL tolerated the test and stayed intact and finally; the EC-CL was partly damaged at the edges of the layer (Fig. 2b). It proves that elastomer polymer in SBS-CL

act the best to stick the paste components uniformly together compared to PMMA binder in PMMA-CL and ethyl cellulose binder and P25 nanoparticles in EC-CL. Afterward, the test was repeated for the SBS-CL layer in acidic deionized water (with a PH of ~2). The same result with no drawback was obtained (Fig. S1). Consistency and solidity of the SBS-CL as a result of the adhesion test verify the constituents of the SBS-CP are firmly stucked together which is beneficial to resist infiltrating moisture to the substrate and act as internal passivation in PSCs.

Fig. 2. Appearance of the PMMA-CL, SBS-CL, and EC-CL before (top image) and after (bottom image) a) the adhesion test, b) the ultrasonication test, c) the flexibility test: resistance of the layers versus bending cycles.

Flexible electrodes are promising for commercial objectives in solar cell technology due to their mechanical robustness. To measure the mechanical flexibility of deposited layers of each carbon

paste, the samples were prepared by doctor-blading the pastes onto a flexible substrate which can withstand the temperature of 100 °C for annealing. The mechanical flexibility of the three carbon layers was measured by periodically bending (with the curvature radius of about 4 mm) the samples and measuring the variation of the resistivity (MP4 file in supporting information). Despite the low resistivity, the PMMA-CL was too fragile to bend for 2 times, and the layer was broken. The EC-CL also had similar behavior in response to bending. Therefore, with both lack of flexibility and high resistivity, EC-CP is not viable. For the sample related to SBS-CL, the sheet resistance is almost unchanged after 1017 bending cycles while the layer is completely intact and no fracture has occurred during the measurement (the video in supplementary shows the procedure of the measurement). Fig 2c shows the resistivity of each layer based on bending cycles. The flexibility of carbon paste depends on several factors which are the ratio of carbon particles (it means the ratio of graphite to carbon black nanoparticles), the concentration of carbon paste, and importantly the applied binder. From the results of fig 2 an appropriate combination of the factors can be observed for the SBS-CL and the conductive part is well embedded in the binder.

To gain further insight into their performance as hole collector electrodes in PSCs and compatibility with the perovskite layer, the n-i-p-based PSCs with an active area of 0.096 cm² (FTO/TiO₂-compact/meso-TiO₂/perovskite/CuInS₂/Carbon) were fabricated (The specified measurements of TEM, UV-visible light transmittance, Tauc plot, and XRD related to CIS nanoparticles were carried out as shown in Fig. S2 and S3 and EDS analysis is tabulated in Table S2.) and the corresponding photovoltaic properties were investigated under AM 1.5 light illumination conditions. Fig. S4 demonstrates the surface SEM of the bare perovskite layer and also the coverage of CIS NPs onto that alongside related cross-sectional SEM and finally the

schematic structure of the device. The appearance of perovskite layer did not change after the deposition of all three carbon electrodes. The best performing photovoltaic characteristics of the solar cells based on PMMA-CP, SBS-CP, and EC-CP (PMMA-PSCs, SBS-PSCs, and EC-PSCs) are listed in Table 2. The results indicate no practical performance for the EC-PSCs, as shown in Fig. 3a. The incapability of the electrode in terms of transferring the charge carrier is beyond its high electrical resistivity. It may refer to the corrosion at the interface of the hole conductor electrode and perovskite layer which is the drawback of the solvent component (terpineol) in the paste. The corrosion forms a discontinuity hindering transferring charge carriers. Therefore, it can be concluded the EC-CP doesn't act as a hole collector electrode in the fabricated PSCs and the device is degraded as soon as applying EC-CP onto it in the final step of the fabrication. Hence, fabricating EC-PSCs were stopped (repetitively the fabrication was considered for PMMA and SBS-PSCs) and further measurements weren't carried out for the mentioned devices. However, the efficiency of the PMMA and SBS-PSCs was recorded until they were measurable.

Fig. 3. a) Current density-voltage under one sun illumination, b) The IPCE and integrated J_{sc} curves of the best device of each group and, c) Distribution of measured efficiencies of CPSCs based on three different carbon paste, d) Steady-state PCE over 120 s for CPSCs with different CuInS₂/carbon hole collectors.

The best efficiencies for the PMMA and SBS-PSCs rose from as-fabricated values of 12.15% and 16.14% to 14.8% and 17.3% respectively over 4 days (Fig. 3a and Table S3). This increment may originate from the entanglement of the HTL and carbon layer enhancing their interface in the meanwhile. In according to Table S4, a summarize of literatures results regarding carbon-based perovskite solar cells in n-i-p structure, existence of an interface between carbon electrode

and perovskite layer has a crucial role in photovoltaic performance. The best efficiencies concerned to PSCs with Spiro-MeOTAD as an HTL and/or interlayers to modify the interface of HTL and carbon electrode which are higher than HTL-free PSCs. Therefore, existing an appropriate interface to make charge transfer feasible is important. It is noteworthy the significant difference between PMMA, SBS, and EC-PSCs efficiencies confirms the main reason of different interfaces the HTL formed with carbon layer originating from their composition.

A notable improvement in the open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and fill factor (FF) were observed in SBS-PSCs compared with PMMA-PSCs where V_{oc} increases from 1.02 to 1.09 V and FF increases from 0.59 to 0.65 for the PMMA-PSCs and SBS-PSCs respectively. Considering the identical perovskite in both kinds of device and subsequently, the same bandgap energy, the increase in V_{oc} might be attributed to the retarded charge recombination and decreasing V_{oc} loss originated from continuous interface and connection between the perovskite and hole collector electrode facilitating charge carrier transfer. Regarding the SEM images, adhesion, and flexibility tests of the pastes, the SBS-CL had a monolithic coverage without any voids, resilient structure against peeling off the tapes, and ultrasonicate while the PMMA-CL undergoes non-uniform coverage due to cavities and was too fragile and flimsy to stick to the substrate. Although the resistivity of the PMMA-CL was much lower than the SBS-CL, the high quality of the adhesion and coverage forming an interface without cavities and connection between the hole collector and perovskite layer has an important effect on reducing series resistance in the whole device. The results from the measurements related to the carbon pastes well coincided with the results of the photovoltaic characterization. Fig. 3b shows the verification of J_{sc} values by comparing the spectrum of the incident photons to current conversion efficiency (IPCE) measured for each optimal condition. The values of the integrated J_{sc} were 21.85, 22.47, and 1.68

mA cm⁻² for the PMMA-PSCs, SBS-PSCs, and EC-PSCs, respectively. The IPCE response for the SBS-PSC is slightly higher than the one for the PMMA-PSC. The reason might be attributed to the strong adhesion of the SBS-CP to the substrate which can have an influence on improving the interface by passivation of the pinholes (this effect is in consistent with the results of published papers in this area[32]). The stabilized power output curves of two samples of PMMA-PSCs and SBS-PSCs under the maximum power conditions were measured under light soaking in ambient air at around a relative humidity of 30–40% and filtering the infrared (IR) part of the radiation to avoid absorbing the spectrum and consequently heating the carbon electrode, as shown in Fig. 3d (light soaking tracking was done at V_{oc}). From the statistics of the PV performance parameters (J_{sc} , V_{oc} , FF (Fig. S5), and PCE (Fig. 3c)) for three kinds of PSCs, higher values of V_{oc} and J_{sc} (where the average V_{oc} of the PMMA-PSCs and SBS-PSCs are 1.03 and 1.09 V and the corresponding average J_{sc} are 20.5 and 22.9 mA cm⁻²) can be generally observed for SBS-CP based PSCs confirming the lower series resistant and better interface between the perovskite layer and hole collector electrode in the respective devices. The SBS-PSCs also showed elevated reproducibility in all photovoltaic properties relative to PMMA ones. The higher values of V_{oc} can also be attributed to the proper internal passivation of charge traps by SBS-CP causing improved extraction of hole carriers.

To further study the charge transport behavior at the interface formed between perovskite and CIS/Carbon electrode owing to PMMA-CP and SBS-CP, electrical impedance spectroscopy was employed. The record of the impedance spectra of PSCs was done under 0.1 sun illumination of a white LED source for different applied DC potential (V_{oc} , 0.8, 0.6, 0.4, 0.2, 0 V) in the frequency range of 0.1 Hz–1 MHz using a 20 mV AC perturbation. The fitted equivalent circuit model as shown in Fig. S6 is composed of several resistors (R) (including series resistance (R_s))

and charge-recombination resistance (R_{rec}) and constant phase elements (CPE) and an inductor (L).

Fig. 4. (a) Ohmic Resistance, (b) Charge transport resistances at the interface of PSK/ CIS-carbon hole collector (c) Impedance spectra of PMMA-PSCs, (d) Impedance spectra of SBS-PSCs obtained under 0.1 sun illumination of LED light source for different applied DC potential (V_{oc} , 0.8, 0.6, 0.4, 0.2 ,0 V) using impedance spectroscopy.

CPE_1 and R_1 are referred to the charge accumulation at the electrode interfaces in the low frequency while CPE_3 and R_3 are associated with the formed capacitance and charge transfer resistance at the interface of the PSK layer and HTL. The internal slow processes in the PSK

layer related to the kinetic of ions are shown with CPE_2 and R_2 elements[22,33]. Despite the fact, the mentioned representatives of EIS responses cannot specifically be responsible for a process due to the overlapping of different phenomena on each other. Fig. 4c and 4d show the results of EIS for each device at V_{oc} condition as well as different applied biases (between the open and short circuit) to cover different conditions of Fermi level splitting. Considering the issue of the PSCs stabilities, low fixed illumination (0.1 SUN) along with sweeping the fermi level splitting was preferred rather than using different illumination power densities at the fixed V_{oc} condition[34]. EIS parameters of PSCs with different HTMs are summarized in Table S5 and S6. Regarding the similarity of two kinds of devices in the ETL and PSK layer, it is assumed that the dynamics of the carriers in terms of charge transfer resistance are attributed to PSK/CIS-hole conductor electrodes.

Charge transfer resistance at the interface is involved in series resistance. It is observed from Fig. 4a series resistance for SBS-PSCs is lower than the one for PMMA-PSCs in the whole voltage interval indicating a lower recombination rate at the interface of PSK layer and hole collector electrode. Regarding the PMMA-PSC graph, formation a loop in intermediate frequency region can be observed. According literature these effects happens for systems with not efficient charge extraction contact and the inductive loop would be more pronounced for PSCs with poorer performance[35]. Therefore, this graph sheds light on the cause of different V_{oc} and FF obtained from two different hole collector electrodes-based devices where facilitated charge transfer may result in higher FF .

To further investigate the recombination process, V_{oc} decay characterization was employed. To avoid the transient effect of ion movement and filling slow traps, stabilizing the V_{oc} under illumination is important. Afterward, the decay of the V_{oc} by instantly switching the lamp off is

measured[36,37]. The rapid decay of the voltage can be observed due to fast radiative and non-radiative recombination of the photo-generated charge carriers. The fast decay follows by the slow decay displaying long carrier lifetime of charge carriers. Fig. 5a shows the record of the V_{oc} decay as a function of time. By considering the following equation:

$$\tau_n = k_B T / q (dV_{oc}/dt)^{-1},$$

where k_B is Boltzmann constant, T is absolute temperature, and q is the elementary charge[38], it can be concluded the SBS-PSC decays much slower than the PMMA-PSC. The slower decay can refer to the retarded non-radiative recombination and longer carrier life time[39,40]. The data is in consistent with the internal passivation of the SBS-CP of the defects in the interface of perovskite and hole collector electrode.

Fig. 5. a) V_{oc} -decay over 100 s and, b) Steady-state PCE over 120 s for C-PSCs with different CuInS₂/carbon hole collectors, c,d) Diagrams of distributions of measured efficiency of CPSCs with 2-layer carbon electrode for about 6 months.

Subsequently, dark J - V measurements (Fig. 5b) for devices based on PMMA-CP and SBS-CP were conducted as a verification of our previous results related to the recombination process by fitting the dark J - V curve to the following equation:

$$J_{dark} = J_0 \left(\exp\left(\frac{eV}{nk_B T}\right) - 1 \right)$$

where n is the ideality factor, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature, e is the elementary charge, and J_0 is the dark saturation current. The inverse of the slope of the dark J - V graph near the short and open-circuit regions delivered series resistance (R_s), and shunt resistance (R_{sh}). The fitted parameters are listed in Table S7. The calculation reveals a lower R_s ($25 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$) and higher shunt resistance ($9.36 \times 10^5 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$) for the BC-PSC than those of the PMMA-PSC with the amount of $R_s = 100 \Omega$, $R_{sh} = 1.18 \times 10^5 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$. The higher shunt resistance of SBS-PSC is the result of suppressing trap-assisted charge recombination and decreased leakage current which enhances the V_{oc} . Moreover, the lower R_s in the SBS-PSC than in the PMMA-PSC (in agreement with the results of R_s and R_{sh} from EIS) causes higher photocurrent density[41].

By comparing the two dark J - V curves, more defects can be appraised for the SBS-PSC than the PMMA-PSC. Defects in solar cells result in increased dark current. The values of J_0 for AC and SBS-PSCs were calculated 5.13×10^{-6} and 4.42×10^{-7} Respectively. The decreased J_0 means the combination of CuInS_2 and BC paste is more useful to suppress the recombination in the interface of perovskite and hole collector electrode[32,42–44].

The long-term stability of the PSCs based on PMMA-CP and SBS-CP was monitored at different time intervals. The devices were kept in a dark and ambient atmosphere with a humidity of about 40% after each measurement.

An enhancement in efficiency for both of them can be observed till they were measurable. After the 40th day, the contacts of the PMMA-PSCs were broken and it was impossible to continue the test for the PMMA-PSCs while the SBS-PSC exhibited sterling stability and rising trend with the best efficiency of 18.6% on 65th day and after 172 they were still intact in appearance along with a slight decline in its initial efficiency. The long-term stability regarding the SBS-PSC verified the effect of the internal passivation of the SBS-CP onto the perovskite layer. The relative

degradation of the PMMA-PSC may refer to irreversible morphological degradation features including forming voids and delamination of the electrode. Additionally, to further confirm what was claimed, two devices of the PMMA-PSC and SBS-PSC were immersed in the water for about 5 minutes. The PMMA-PSC was completely degraded and the perovskite layer even the part covered by the carbon electrode turned to yellow. The degradation into the yellow phase also happened in the case of SBS-PSC, but the part covered by the carbon electrode didn't change, as shown in Fig. S7 this noticeable observation is another verification to what have discussed in this paper.

To further explore the stability and the scalability of the carbon-based devices (SBS), we compared the performance of SBS-CP and a widely used commercial carbon paste (Dyename) as back electrodes on large area cells by adopting the low temperature planar stack and the related scalable related scalable deposition processes reported before[45,46]. Here, the active area is about 0.5 cm^2 and the full stack was deposited using doctor blade method with a dimension of 37.7 cm^2 in ambient air, except for CIS layer deposited by spin coating method. The best efficiency of 10.69% and 14.9% were obtained for the SBS and Dyename carbon electrode-based device, respectively. Despite the lower efficiency, the SBS electrode-based devices are more reproducible. Fig. S8a and S8b shows the statistics results regarding the stability of the devices. According to the results, the SBS-PSC based devices are more stable and reproducible. The JV curve and related IPCE of the best device in each group are demonstrated in Fig. S8c and S8d, respectively. Some devices weren't intact after 4 days to be measured, so there are some vanished points in the distribution graph. Therefore, using SBS-CP as an electrode in perovskite solar cells deliver more stable devices without any encapsulation.

4. Conclusion:

In this study, three distinct carbon pastes were investigated to determine the optimal carbon electrode concerning conductivity, mechanical properties, and its performance as a back electrode in a PSC. These carbon pastes were differentiated based on their binders, solvents, and conductive components. The carbon electrodes were incorporated into the structure of regular n-i-p PSCs. While all three pastes share similarities in conductive components (a mixture of carbon black and graphite flakes), the influence of the binder and solvent on the chemical and rheological qualities of the PSK/HTL/C interface played a crucial role in determining the mechanical and photovoltaic performance of the electrodes. In terms of mechanical strength, three tests of adhesion, application of ultrasound and flexural cycles were evaluated. Although the PMMA-CP was superior in conductivity to the other two pastes, it performed poorly concerning mechanical strength. The thermoplastic elastomer polymer-based paste, SBS-CP, successfully passed all strength tests and maintained its performance after applying more than 1000 bending cycles. Regarding photovoltaic performance, the commercial paste containing terpineol did not provide photovoltaic feedback due to chemical incompatibility and possible corrosion at the interface. For the other two pastes, the best results for PMMA-PSCs and SBS-PSCs were 12.15% and 16.14%, respectively, which increased to 14.8% and 17.3% over 4 days. Also, a significant improvement in open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and charge coefficient (FF) was observed in SBS-PSCs compared to PMMA-PSCs where V_{oc} increased from 1.02 to 1.09 V and FF from 0.59 to 0.65. The increase in V_{oc} may be due to the delay in recombination of the charge carriers and the reduction in V_{oc} losses due to the continuous interface and the better connection between the perovskite and the hole collector electrode, which facilitates the transfer of the charge carrier.

Acknowledgments:

This research was partially funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe program, through a FET Proactive research and innovation action under grant agreement No. 101084124 (DIAMOND).

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